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The Relationship between Academic Stress, Cognitive Reappraisal, Sleep Quality, and Living Status among University Students

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Abstract: *The present study examined the relationship among academic stress, cognitive reappraisal, sleep quality, and living status among university students in Pakistan. A quantitative, cross-sectional research design was employed with a sample of 300 university students (M = 150, F = 150) drawn from public and private universities of the Federal and Punjab regions of Pakistan, using a non-probability purposive sampling technique. Academic stress was measured using the Perception of Academic Stress Scale (Bedewy & Gabriel, 2015), cognitive reappraisal was measured using the cognitive reappraisal subscale of the Emotion Regulation Questionnaire (Gross & John, 2003), and sleep quality was measured using the Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (Buysse et al., 1989). Living status was assessed through a self-constructed demographic information sheet and categorized into home, hostel, and living alone. The findings revealed that living status was significantly associated with academic stress, cognitive reappraisal, and sleep quality. Students residing in hostels reported higher academic stress and poorer sleep quality, while students living at home reported higher cognitive reappraisal and better sleep quality than hostel residents and those living alone. The findings suggest that the residential environment of university students plays an important role in shaping their psychological functioning, emotional regulation capacity, and sleep-related outcomes. The implications of the study highlight the need for university counseling centers to design supportive interventions, including sleep hygiene education and emotion regulation training, particularly for students residing in hostels and those living independently.*

Keywords: Academic Stress, Cognitive Reappraisal, Sleep Quality, Living Status.

Introduction

The transition to university life represents a critical developmental period, often described as emerging adulthood, occurring between the ages of 18 and 25 years (Arnett, 2000). The period is characterized by increased independence, identity formation, and exposure to new academic, social, and residential demands, which together place university students at heightened risk for psychological strain (Pascoe et al., 2020). Among the many challenges faced during this stage, academic stress, emotion regulation difficulties, and disrupted sleep have emerged as central concerns for student mental health and well-being.

Academic Stress refers to the psychological strain that arises when academic demands, such as examinations, assignments, workload, and performance expectations, exceed the coping resources available to the individual (Bedewy & Gabriel, 2015; Misra & McKean, 2000). University students are particularly susceptible to academic stress because of the cumulative pressures of examinations, deadlines, and performance competition, alongside sociocultural expectations such as parental pressure and concerns about future employment, which are especially salient in the Pakistani context (Pascoe et al., 2020).

One of the psychological mechanisms through which students manage academic stress is emotion regulation. Among the strategies identified within Gross and John's (2003) process model of emotion regulation, cognitive reappraisal is considered an adaptive, antecedent focused strategy that involves reinterpreting the meaning of a stressful situation in order to reduce its emotional impact. Higher levels of cognitive reappraisal have been associated with reduced emotional reactivity, improved coping, and better psychological adjustment under conditions of academic pressure (Gross & John, 2003).

Sleep Quality, defined as the subjective experience of how restorative and uninterrupted one's sleep is, rather than merely its duration, is another important indicator of student well being (Buysse et al., 1989). University students are considered a vulnerable population for poor sleep quality due to academic stress, irregular schedules, and disrupted routines associated with university life (Hershner & Chervin, 2014; Lund et al., 2010). Poor sleep quality has been linked to reduced concentration, emotional instability, and impaired academic performance (Medic et al., 2017).

An overlooked contextual factor that may shape all three of these variables is students' living status, that is, whether a student resides at home with family, in a university hostel, or independently. The residential environment determines the level of social support, privacy, noise exposure, shared responsibilities, and access to familiar routines, all of which can influence how students experience academic stress, regulate their emotions, and sleep (Hershner & Chervin, 2014; Lund et al., 2010). In collectivist cultural contexts such as Pakistan, family living arrangements are thought to provide a protective buffer of social support that may not be available to students living in hostels or alone (Rehman et al., 2021).

While considerable research has examined academic stress, emotion regulation, and sleep quality separately, relatively little attention has been given to how these variables differ according to students' living arrangements, particularly within the university context of Pakistan. Understanding these differences has practical relevance for university administrations, as it can help identify which groups of students may require targeted psychological support. Therefore, the present study aims to examine the relationship among

academic stress, cognitive reappraisal, sleep quality, and living status among university students in Pakistan.

Literature Review

Academic Stress

Academic Stress is a multidimensional psychological phenomenon that arises when academic demands perceived by an individual exceed their coping resources and capabilities, and when these demands are appraised as a threat rather than as an objective workload (Misra & McKean, 2000). University students are particularly exposed to academic stress due to continuous exposure to examinations, deadlines, assignments, and performance evaluations, all of which require sustained cognitive and emotional engagement (Beiter et al., 2015). Academic stress can be acute, arising from short term stressors such as exams, or chronic, developing over time due to sustained academic pressure and workload (Misra & McKean, 2000).

Academic stressors are typically categorized into external factors, such as workload, deadlines, examination pressure, and parental expectations, and internal factors, such as perfectionism, fear of failure, and low perceived academic competence (Beiter et al., 2015). The consequences of academic stress span psychological domains, including anxiety, irritability, and emotional exhaustion, as well as behavioral domains, such as procrastination and avoidance, and academic domains, including reduced concentration and memory (Misra & McKean, 2000).

In Pakistan, academic stress is reported to be especially common due to sociocultural and structural factors, including high parental expectations, societal pressure to excel academically, and limited career prospects, all of which contribute to academic stress emerging as a major mental health concern among university students (Rehman et al., 2021).

Cognitive Reappraisal

Cognitive Reappraisal is one of the two primary emotion regulation strategies identified within Gross and John's (2003) process model of emotion regulation, the other being expressive suppression. Cognitive reappraisal is an antecedent focused, adaptive coping strategy that involves reinterpreting the meaning of a potentially stressful situation in a way that alters its emotional impact before the emotional response is fully developed (Gross & John, 2003).

Higher levels of cognitive reappraisal are associated with students' ability to view academic challenges as manageable demands rather than as threats, thereby lowering emotional intensity and improving adaptive coping (Gross & John, 2003). Cognitive reappraisal functions as a buffering mechanism that can minimize the negative psychological impact of academic stress. Emotion regulation more broadly is recognized as an important determinant of psychological adaptation, particularly in chronically stressful contexts such as academic environments (Aldao et al., 2010).

Within the sociocultural context of Pakistan, emotion regulation, including the use of cognitive reappraisal, is shaped by competitive educational settings, high academic pressure, and cultural norms surrounding emotional expression, which may influence the extent to which students rely on reappraisal as a coping resource (Aldao et al., 2010; Rehman et al., 2021).

Sleep Quality

Sleep Quality refers to a subjective rating of an individual's sleep experience, encompassing sleep initiation, continuity, duration, and restfulness, rather than the number of hours slept alone (Buysse et al., 1989). Poor sleep quality is characterized by difficulty falling asleep, frequent nighttime awakenings, early morning awakening, and non-restorative sleep that results in daytime fatigue and impaired functioning (Medic et al., 2017).

University students represent one of the most vulnerable populations for poor sleep quality due to academic stress, irregular schedules, and the psychological demands of university life (Lund et al., 2010). The transition to university typically involves increased autonomy, heavier workloads, and reduced parental oversight, all of which can disrupt sleep patterns and circadian stability (Hershner & Chervin, 2014). Lifestyle factors such as excessive screen time and late night studying further contribute to sleep disturbances among students (Exelmans & Van den Bulck, 2016).

Sleep Quality has wide ranging psychological, cognitive, and academic implications. Poor sleep is associated with irritability, anxiety, and reduced well being, as well as impaired attention, working memory, and academic performance (Medic et al., 2017). In Pakistan specifically, poor sleep quality among university students has been linked to academic stress, sociocultural expectations, and a general lack of awareness regarding sleep hygiene (Hershner & Chervin, 2014; Rehman et al., 2021).

Living Status

Living Status, referring to whether university students reside at home with their families, in university hostels, or independently and alone, represents an important contextual variable that may shape students' experiences of academic stress, their emotion regulation capacity, and the quality of their sleep. The residential environment determines the degree of social support, privacy, structure, and exposure to shared facilities and disturbances, all of which have implications for psychological functioning (Hershner & Chervin, 2014; Lund et al., 2010).

The hostel environments, in particular, are often characterized by shared rooms, communal facilities, peer related social pressures, and reduced privacy, which have been associated with poorer sleep quality due to noise and lack of personal space (Hershner & Chervin, 2014; Lund et al., 2010). In contrast, home environments, particularly within collectivist cultures such as Pakistan, may provide a protective effect through family social support, structured routines, and quieter living conditions, which can foster more adaptive emotion regulation and better sleep (Rehman et al., 2021).

Despite the theoretical relevance of living status to students' psychological outcomes, living status has received comparatively limited empirical attention in the literature on academic stress, emotion regulation, and sleep quality, particularly within the university context of Pakistan. Examining how academic stress, cognitive reappraisal, and sleep quality differ across living arrangements can therefore provide important insights for designing context sensitive student support services.

Rationale of the Study

Although academic stress, cognitive reappraisal, and sleep quality have each been studied extensively, the role of living status as a contextual factor influencing these variables remains underexplored, particularly in non-Western settings such as Pakistan. University students in

Pakistan reside in diverse arrangements, including family homes, hostels, and independent living. It is important to examine whether these residential contexts are associated with meaningful differences in academic stress, cognitive reappraisal, and sleep quality. Identifying such differences can help universities and hostel administrations design targeted psychological interventions for the groups of students who may be most at risk.

Research Question

Is there a significant relationship between academic stress, cognitive reappraisal, sleep quality, and living status among university students?

Method

Research Design

The study employed a quantitative, cross-sectional research design to examine the relationship among academic stress, cognitive reappraisal, sleep quality, and living status among university students.

Sample

The sample consisted of 300 university students (150 male, 150 female) drawn from public and private sector universities in the Federal and Punjab regions of Pakistan. A non-probability purposive sampling technique was used to recruit participants. The age range of participants was 18 to 25 years, corresponding to the developmental period of emerging adulthood (Arnett, 2000).

Inclusion criteria required that participants be full-time enrolled undergraduate or postgraduate university students, aged between 18 and 25 years, able to read and comprehend English, and willing to provide informed consent. Students with a self-reported history of psychiatric or sleep disorders, those currently using prescribed sleep medication, and part-time students were excluded from the study.

Instruments

In addition to a demographic information sheet that recorded participants' living status, the following standardized instruments were used to measure the study variables.

Perception of Academic Stress Scale (PAS)

Academic Stress was measured using the Perception of Academic Stress (PAS) Scale developed by Bedewy and Gabriel (2015). The scale consists of 18 items across three subscales: academic expectations, workload and examinations, and academic self-perception. Items are rated on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree), with items 1 to 5 reverse-coded. Total scores range from 18 to 90, with higher scores indicating greater perceived academic stress. The scale has demonstrated good psychometric properties, with reported Cronbach's alpha values ranging between .70 and .85 (Bedewy & Gabriel, 2015).

Emotion Regulation Questionnaire (ERQ) – Cognitive Reappraisal Subscale

Cognitive reappraisal was measured using the cognitive reappraisal subscale of the Emotion Regulation Questionnaire (ERQ), developed by Gross and John (2003). The full ERQ comprises 10 items across two subscales, cognitive reappraisal (6 items) and expressive suppression (4 items), rated on a 7-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 7 (Strongly Agree). The cognitive reappraisal subscale has demonstrated acceptable reliability, with reported Cronbach’s alpha values ranging between .79 and .84 (Gross & John, 2003).

Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI)

Sleep quality was measured using the Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI), developed by Buysse et al. (1989). The PSQI consists of 19 items organized into seven components: subjective sleep quality, sleep latency, sleep duration, habitual sleep efficiency, sleep disturbances, use of sleep medication, and daytime dysfunction. Items are rated on a 4-point scale ranging from 0 (Not during the past month) to 3 (Three or more times a week). Component scores are combined to yield a global score ranging from 0 to 21, with higher scores indicating poorer sleep quality. The PSQI has demonstrated good internal consistency, with a reported Cronbach’s alpha of .83 (Buysse et al., 1989).

Demographic Information Sheet

In addition to a demographic information sheet that recorded participants’ living status A self-constructed demographic information sheet was used to gather information about participants’ living status. The living status was categorized into three groups: living at home, living in a hostel, and living alone.

Procedure

Data were collected through a combination of in-person questionnaire distribution and an online survey link administered across public and private universities in the Federal and Punjab regions of Pakistan. Participants were informed about the purpose of the study and assured that their participation was voluntary, anonymous, and confidential, and that they could withdraw at any time without consequence. Informed consent was obtained from all participants before data collection. Responses were screened for completeness and eligibility before data analysis.

Results

To examine differences in academic stress, cognitive reappraisal, and sleep quality across living status, a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted. The results are presented in Tables 1 and 2.

Table 1

Mean Differences across Living Status among Study Variables (N = 300).

Variables	Home (n =157)		Hostel (n = 116)		Alone (n =27)		f	p	η ²
	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD			
AS	51.03	8.26	52.51	10.88	43.44	6.78	10.52	.00	.07
CR	29.11	6.95	24.88	7.12	28.44	4.19	13.16	.00	.08
ES	17.71	4.50	17.01	5.96	18.93	2.41	1.79	.17	-
SQ	5.76	3.33	7.09	3.38	7.67	3.62	7.06	.00	.05

*p < .05, **p < .01, ***p < .001.

Note: M = Mean, SD = Standard Deviation, f= Frequency, p = Significance Level, AS = Academic Stress, SQ = Sleep Quality, CR = Cognitive Reappraisal, ES = Expressive Suppression.

Table 1 represents the mean differences of the study variables by the living status of 300 participants. The findings indicated significant differences in academic stress, $F = 10.52, p < .001, \eta^2 = .07$. Participants living in hostels ($M = 52.51, SD = 10.88$) reported higher academic stress compared to those living at home ($M = 51.03, SD = 8.26$) and those living alone ($M = 43.44, SD = 6.78$).

Significant differences were also observed in cognitive reappraisal across living status, $F = 13.16, p < .001, \eta^2 = .08$. Participants living at home reported the highest cognitive reappraisal scores ($M = 29.11, SD = 6.95$), followed by those living alone ($M = 28.44, SD = 4.19$), while hostel residents reported the lowest cognitive reappraisal scores ($M = 24.88, SD = 7.12$).

About sleep quality, significant differences emerged across living status, $F = 7.06, p < .001, \eta^2 = .05$. Participants living alone reported the poorest sleep quality, that is, the highest PSQI scores ($M = 7.67, SD = 3.62$), followed by hostel residents ($M = 7.09, SD = 3.38$), while participants living at home reported the best sleep quality, that is, the lowest PSQI scores ($M = 5.76, SD = 3.33$).

Overall, the findings indicate that living status was significantly related to academic stress, cognitive reappraisal, and sleep quality among university students, with hostel residents and students living alone consistently showing less favorable scores on these variables compared to students living at home.

Table 2

Hochberg Post Hoc Analysis of Study Variables across Living Status (N = 300).

Groups	Groups		Mean Difference	SE	p	95% CI	
	I	J	I-J			LL	UL
AS	Home	Hostel	-1.483	1.134	0.471	-4.2	1.24
	Home	Alone	7.581*	1.929	0	2.95	12.21
	Hostel	Alone	9.064*	1.979	0	4.31	13.81
CR	Home	Hostel	4.229*	0.835	0	2.22	6.23
	Home	Alone	0.664	1.421	0.953	-2.75	4.08
	Hostel	Alone	-3.565*	1.458	0.044	-7.07	-0.07
SQ	Home	Hostel	-1.322*	0.413	0.005	-2.31	-0.33
	Home	Alone	-1.902*	0.703	0.021	-3.59	-0.21
	Hostel	Alone	-0.58	0.721	0.806	-2.31	1.15

* $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$.

Note: SE = Significant Error, p = Significance Level, CI = Confidence Interval, LL = Lower Level, UL = Upper Level, AS = Academic Stress, SQ = Sleep Quality, CR = Cognitive Appraisal.

Table 2 shows the Hochberg post hoc analysis of study variables by living status for 300 participants. The findings showed significant differences between the academic stress of the participants in the home ($MD = 7.58, p < .001$) and between the academic stress of the participants in the hostel ($MD = 9.06, p < .001$). The academic stress was significantly lower among the participants who live alone than among those who live at home and in hostels. The report scores were significantly higher for those living at home than for those living in the hostels ($MD = 4.23, p < .001$) for cognitive reappraisal. Further, participants who lived alone also had higher cognitive reappraisal than those who lived in hostels ($MD = -3.57, p < .05$). For sleep quality, participants in the hostels group had a significantly poorer score than those living at home ($MD = -1.32, p < .001$), and participants living alone had a significantly poorer score

than those living at home ($MD = -1.90, p < .05$). Those who were living in the hostels and those who were alone reported having poorer sleep quality than those living at home.

Discussion

The present study examined the relationship among academic stress, cognitive reappraisal, sleep quality, and living status among university students in Pakistan. It was hypothesized that there would be significant differences in academic stress, cognitive reappraisal, and sleep quality across living status. The results provided strong support for the hypothesis, as significant ANOVA results were obtained across all three variables.

Students living in hostels reported significantly higher academic stress compared to those living at home, and both groups reported higher academic stress than students living alone. In addition, students living at home reported significantly higher cognitive reappraisal than hostel residents, and students living at home also reported significantly better sleep quality than both hostel residents and those living alone. These findings are consistent with previous research, which has found that residents of dormitories and hostels report significantly poorer sleep quality due to noise, lack of privacy, and disrupted routines (Hershner & Chervin, 2014; Lund et al., 2010).

The poorer outcomes observed among hostel residents may be explained by the characteristics typical of university hostel environments in Pakistan, including shared facilities, shared responsibilities, peer related social pressures, and disruptions during nighttime hours, all of which can negatively affect both sleep quality and the cognitive resources required for adaptive emotion regulation, such as cognitive reappraisal (Hershner & Chervin, 2014; Rehman et al., 2021).

In contrast, the more favorable outcomes observed among students living at home may reflect the protective role of family social support, which has been emphasized as a particularly important psychological resource within collectivist cultural contexts such as Pakistan (Rehman et al., 2021). Home environments may also tend to be quieter and more structured than hostel environments, which could foster conditions conducive to adaptive cognitive regulation and better sleep (Gross & John, 2003).

The finding that students living alone reported the lowest academic stress, yet also reported relatively poor sleep quality comparable to hostel residents, suggests that living independently may reduce certain academic and social pressures associated with shared living arrangements, while still presenting challenges to sleep, possibly due to the absence of the structured routines and social support that a family home environment may provide (Hershner & Chervin, 2014; Rehman et al., 2021).

Taken together, these findings highlight that living status is not merely a demographic characteristic but a meaningful contextual factor associated with university students' levels of academic stress, their capacity to engage in adaptive emotion regulation through cognitive reappraisal, and the quality of their sleep.

Implications and Significance

The findings of the present study carry important theoretical and practical implications. Theoretically, the results extend the literature on academic stress, emotion regulation, and sleep quality by demonstrating that students' residential environment is an important contextual

factor associated with these psychological outcomes, supporting the relevance of considering living arrangements within frameworks of student mental health in non-Western, collectivist cultural contexts such as Pakistan.

Practically, the findings suggest that university counseling centers and student support services should give particular attention to students residing in hostels and those living independently, as these groups reported higher academic stress, lower cognitive reappraisal, and poorer sleep quality compared to students living at home. University hostel administrations may consider implementing measures to reduce noise, improve privacy, and create quieter study and rest environments to support better sleep quality among hostel residents.

Furthermore, cognitive reappraisal skill-building programs and sleep hygiene education could be incorporated into student wellness programs, with particular outreach to hostel residents and students living alone, who may have reduced access to the informal support systems available to students living with their families. Such interventions could help to mitigate the less favorable psychological and sleep-related outcomes associated with these living arrangements.

Conclusion

The present study examined the relationship among academic stress, cognitive reappraisal, sleep quality, and living status among 300 university students in Pakistan. The findings demonstrated that living status was significantly associated with all three psychological variables. Students living in hostels reported the highest academic stress and poorest sleep quality, students living at home reported the highest cognitive reappraisal and best sleep quality, and students living alone reported the lowest academic stress but relatively poor sleep quality. These findings underscore the importance of students' residential environment in shaping their psychological well-being and highlight the need for living status-sensitive support services within university settings in Pakistan.

Limitations

The present study has several limitations that should be acknowledged. First, the cross-sectional design does not allow for causal inferences to be drawn regarding the relationship between living status and the study variables; longitudinal designs would be needed to examine these relationships over time. Second, the sample was drawn using a non-probability purposive sampling technique, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to the broader population of university students in Pakistan. Third, the proportion of students living alone was considerably smaller than the proportions of students living at home or in hostels, which may have affected the statistical power to detect differences involving this group. Finally, several potentially relevant confounding variables, such as the number of roommates, financial stress, and prior sleep disorder history, were not controlled for in the analyses examining living status, and future research should consider examining these factors more systematically.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the present study, it is recommended that universities and hostel administrations in Pakistan develop targeted psychological support programs for students residing in hostels and those living independently, given their relatively higher academic stress and poorer sleep quality. Sleep hygiene education programs should be incorporated into student

orientation and wellness initiatives, with particular emphasis on hostel residents. Cognitive reappraisal training and emotion regulation workshops may also be beneficial, particularly for students who do not have access to the family support systems available to those living at home. Future research should employ longitudinal designs to examine how living status influences academic stress, cognitive reappraisal, and sleep quality over the course of students' academic careers, and should aim to recruit larger samples of students living alone to allow for more robust comparisons across living arrangements.

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